

RESEARCH QUESTION

Does the existence of a performative act contribute to the creation of new fashion show formats?

LITERATURE REVIEW

- . Fashion Show;
- . The Performance;
- . New Media

TRY

OBJECTIVES

METHODOLOGY BASED ON ARTISTIC PRACTICE

COMBINATION OF METHODS

EXPERIENCE

QUALITATIVE METHODOLOGY

#1st_Composition#
Fashion Media&Art I
Fashion Media&Art II

Public Feedback

Critical Analysis of Performances

Performance as Language in a Fashion Show

Data Collection and Analysis

Experimentation / Testing until the desired result is achieved

Analysis of Results and Audience Experience /Discussion

Final Proposal

Fashion Media&Art III

CONCLUSIONS